

Examining the Influence of Teaching Approaches on Students' Entrepreneurial Competencies and Attitudes: A Case Study in The UAEU University

Dr. Ashraf Mohamed Awad

Associate professor of Administration Management, Abu Dhabi University

Mr. Elsaïd Saad Abdelaziz

Instructor of English Language, Abu Dhabi University

ABSTRACT: Purpose – The study aims to examining the influence of teaching approaches on Students' Entrepreneurial Competencies and Attitudes: A Case Study in The UAEU University.

Design/methodology/approaches – The research methodology employed a quantitative approach, utilizing a questionnaire as the primary instrument for data collection. A total of 490 valid questionnaires were gathered from students at UAEU University, yielding an impressive response rate of 98%. To test the hypotheses, structural equation modeling (SEM) was employed as the analytical method.

Findings – The results of this study showed that teaching approaches had insignificant positive effect on the students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship at the United Arab Emirates University. Moreover, teaching approaches had significant positive effect on the entrepreneurial competencies of students at UAEU University. Moreover, the entrepreneurial competencies had significant positive effect on the students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship at UAEU University. Finally, teaching approaches had significant indirect positive effect on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship through entrepreneurial competencies as a mediator.

Originality/value – The findings underscore the importance of adopting innovative teaching methods and fostering entrepreneurial competencies to nurture a positive entrepreneurial mindset among students. By enhancing our understanding of these dynamics, educators can better design entrepreneurship programs that prepare students for the challenges and opportunities of the modern business landscape at the UAEU university.

Implications and Recommendations – The study highlights teaching approaches' positive impact on students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship, mediated by entrepreneurial competencies. Practical implications include tailored curriculum, diverse pedagogical methods, mentorship programs, holistic evaluation, and continuous improvement for fostering entrepreneurial mindsets at UAEU university.

Key words: Teaching approaches, Entrepreneurial competencies, Students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship, UAEU University, Emirates

Introduction
Literature review
Research Design
Analysis & Results
Discussion & Conclusion
Limitation & Future Research
References

1. Introduction

In recent years, entrepreneurship education has become very important in academic curricula in universities all over the world, and in light of the economic and social challenges in the era of globalization, it has become very important to promote entrepreneurial mindset among young people in universities. In this regard, this study aims to examining the impact of teaching approaches on students' competencies and attitudes in the field of entrepreneurship in the context of the United Arab Emirates University. Several scholarly investigations have analyzed the underlying motivations prompting individuals to aspire toward entrepreneurial competencies (Botha, 2024; Kitsios, 2024; Khan et al., 2024). Consequently, many nations have commenced efforts aimed at cultivating and fortifying entrepreneurial initiatives, as governments find themselves unable to solely provide financial stability to their citizenry (Hossain et al., 2023). Entrepreneurship education (EE) has gained heightened significance due to its potential to cultivate innovation and stimulate economic expansion, particularly within the contemporary context of rapid global economic transformations and uncertainty (Nikou et al., 2023). Entrepreneurial teaching in higher education fosters innovation, resilience, and real-world skills to empower students for entrepreneurial endeavors, Entrepreneurial programs within institutions of higher education can be regarded as a mechanism aimed at cultivating individuals who ultimately engender novel opportunities (Schachtebeck & Tselepis, 2024). In this regard, entrepreneurship Education (EE) has garnered considerable attention from both the popular press and academia due to its recognized socio-economic significance. The alignment of teaching strategies with learning objectives ideally rests upon a pedagogical framework that informs both instructional methods and assessment practices associated with the chosen approach (Race, 2019).

Entrepreneurship education significantly facilitates the transition towards sustainable entrepreneurship. Students widely perceive direct interactions with successful entrepreneurs as highly impactful extracurricular activities, while also valuing the usefulness of online activities in this regard (Isac et al., 2023). Although, Entrepreneurial programs within higher education institutions can be regarded as instrumental in cultivating individuals who are capable of generating novel opportunities. Heinze (2020) contends that the predominant focus of entrepreneurship courses lies in the dissemination of theoretical knowledge pertaining to the concept of entrepreneurship, emphasizing teaching and learning endeavors in this domain.

Additionally, Attitudes and beliefs commonly shape intentional or planned behaviors (Jena, 2020). Within the realm of entrepreneurship, 'attitude' refers to the degree to which an individual perceives entrepreneurial endeavors and their outcomes as favorable, valuable, and advantageous (Ajzen, 2002). This research aims to address the existing gap in the literature by examining the impact of teaching approaches on students' entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes. Specifically, it seeks to investigate the extent to which different teaching approaches influence the enhancement of students' ultimate entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes.

In particular, this study addresses the following research questions (1) What is the impact of teaching approaches on students' attitudes in the UAEU university? (2) what is

the impact of teaching approaches on students' entrepreneurial competences in the UAEU university? (3) what is the impact of students' entrepreneurial competences on their attitudes toward entrepreneurship in the UAEU university? (4) what is indirect impact of teaching approaches on students' attitudes through the mediating role of entrepreneurial competences in the UAEU university?

2. Literature Review

Teaching Approaches in Higher Education

The teaching strategy is harmonized with the learning process and ideally supported by a pedagogical philosophy that serves as a foundation for guiding both teaching practices and assessments associated with the chosen approach (Race, 2019). Several studies on entrepreneurship education institutions have recognized the adoption of practical approaches as a commendable strategy (Schachtebeck & Tselepis, 2024; Sitaridis & Kitsios, 2024; San-Martin et al., 2022). The approaches employed in entrepreneurial education may facilitate the cultivation of both the capacity for identifying opportunities and the aptitude for actively pursuing them (Ferrerias-Garcia et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurial Competencies

In the realm of entrepreneurship, the study of entrepreneurial competencies emerges as a crucial area of research. Similar to the concept of generic competency, this field encompasses a diverse array of definitions within scholarly literature, underscoring the breadth and depth of the term's significance. The diversity of definitions and competency frameworks within the realm of entrepreneurship education has led to considerable confusion in both literature and practice. This confusion persists regarding what should be included in academic entrepreneurship courses and which competencies ought to be prioritized for development (Tittel & Terzidis, 2020). In this regard, (Lans et al., 2018) advance the discussion surrounding the notion of entrepreneurial competence by proposing a framework that categorizes such competencies into four distinct domains: cognitive-oriented, functional-oriented, social-oriented, and meta-oriented.

Students' Attitudes towards entrepreneurship

Attitudes refer to the extent to which an individual holds a positive evaluation of entrepreneurship, while perceived behavioral control pertains to one's beliefs regarding their capability to succeed in a new business venture (San-Martin et al., 2022). Moreover, in entrepreneurial settings, subjective norm, recognized as a predictive determinant of entrepreneurial intentions, correlates with the perceived support an individual anticipates from their close network when embarking on an entrepreneurial endeavor and the significance they attribute to such support (Boissin et al., 2011).

Teaching Approaches and Students' Attitudes towards entrepreneurship

The impact of entrepreneurial teaching approaches on students' attitudes has been a subject of scholarly investigation. Previous studies have examined the relationship between pedagogical methods in entrepreneurship education and students' perceptions.

For instance, Antonelli, et al (2024), Fantozzi et al (2024), Gera et al (2024) have contributed to understanding the influence of teaching approaches on students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Additionally, (Al-Qadasi et al., 2024) have explored the role of teachers as key influencers in shaping students' attitudes within the educational environment. Furthermore, Tran et al. (2024) have delved into the connection between teaching approaches and student engagement and learning outcomes. Finally, Robinson et al (2016) and San-Martín et al. (2022) have highlighted the significance of entrepreneurial teaching approaches in cultivating positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship among students. Based on above, the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H1: Teaching approaches has a significant positively effect on students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship in the UAEU university.

Teaching Approaches and Entrepreneurial Competencies

Several researchers investigated the relationship between teaching approaches and the acquisition of entrepreneurial competencies, helping to inform educational practices and curriculum development in entrepreneurship education (Merung et al., 2024; Miço & Cungu, 2023). Sánchez (2013) indicated that entrepreneurship-specific competencies can be influenced by entrepreneurship-specific education, which agreed with several studies (Ferrerias-Garcia et al., 2021; Chaker & Jarraya, 2021). Based on above, the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H2: Teaching approaches has a significant positively effect on Entrepreneurial Competencies in the UAEU university.

Entrepreneurial Competencies and Students' Attitudes

Several studies have explored how the development of entrepreneurial competencies influences students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship. The primary effects of developing entrepreneurial competencies is an increased interest in entrepreneurship among students (Merung et al., 2024; Ferreira et al., 2022). As students acquire the skills and knowledge necessary for entrepreneurial endeavors, they often become more inclined to explore entrepreneurial opportunities and consider entrepreneurship as a viable career option. A group of studies indicated that entrepreneurial competencies have a significant positive effect on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship (Ncube & Matlala, 2024; Kozlinska et al., 2023; Wulandari, 2022). Based on above, the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H3: Entrepreneurial Competencies has a significant positively effect on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship in the UAEU university.

The Mediating Role of Entrepreneurial Competencies

Studies that tested the effect of entrepreneurial competencies as mediating role between teaching approaches and students' attitudes were scarce (Liu et al., 2024; Rojas et al., 2024; Ferro et al., 2024). However, other moderating effects of entrepreneurial competencies have been investigated. Antonelli, et al. (2024) included that students engaged in courses utilizing innovative teaching approaches reported a noticeable

enhancement in entrepreneurial competencies, exhibiting statistically significant variances compared to the control group's outcomes. Further, Maulida et al. (2024) indicated that enhancing the efficacy of entrepreneurship education among students involves fostering learning through immersive experiences, problem-solving exercises, and hands-on applications within an entrepreneurial setting. Based on above, the hypothesis can be developed as follows:

H4: Teaching approaches has indirect significant positively effect on students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship through the mediating role of entrepreneurial competencies in the UAEU university.

Based on the above, the proposed conceptual framework for the study can be explained as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Source: own elaboration.

3. Research Design

Sample and procedures

This study gathered data from students enrolled at the United Arab Emirates University over a nearly two-month period spanning from February to March 2024. A total of 500 questionnaires were distributed across six faculties of the university. The questionnaire comprised two sections: the first section collected demographic information from respondents, while the second section contained the survey questions. Prior to distributing the questionnaires, the researcher enlisted the assistance of lecturers from these faculties to guide students in completing the surveys and to ensure earnest responses. A total of 490 questionnaires were returned, resulting in a response rate of 98%. Following the exclusion of invalid responses, the final sample consisted of 474 valid questionnaires. Table (1) illustrates the distribution of the research sample across faculties at the United Arab Emirates University.

Table 1: The sample distribution of faculties

Faculty	Population size	percentage	Sample size	Returned questionnaires	Valid questionnaires
Commerce	2747	50.9%	173	171	169
Engineering	1105	21.3%	109	107	102
Computers and inf.	392	7.6%	81	80	77
Pharmacy	397	7.7%	53	52	49
Fine Arts	235	4.6%	46	43	41
Agriculture	329	7.9%	38	37	36
Total	5205	100%	500	490	474

Source: own elaboration.

Table 2 shows the demographic characteristics of the sample. It reveals that among the respondents, 313 were male (66%) and 161 were female (34%). Moreover, a majority of respondents, 69%, fell into the under-25 age group, while 31% belonged to the older age group. Regarding educational attainment, 11.8% of students had less than undergraduate qualifications, 51% were undergraduates, and 37.2% were postgraduates. However, the demographic variable of Faculty was detailed in Table 1.

Table 2: Demographic variables of the sample

Variables	Categories	N	%
Gender	Male	313	66%
	Female	161	34%
Age Group	Less than 25 Yrs.	327	69%,
	25 Yrs. and more	147	31%
Educational Attainment	Less than Undergraduate	53	11.8%
	Undergraduate	241	51%
	Postgraduate	180	37.2%

Source: own elaboration.

Measure

Teaching approaches (TA) were measure using ten-items scale adopted from (San-Martín et al., 2022; Al-Qadasi et al., 2024). Participants indicated the extent to which they felt that entrepreneurship teaching approaches and the quality of the programmes led them to view entrepreneurship in general as more desirable and feasible (e.g. “the university teaching approaches sparked my interest in becoming an entrepreneur”). Each item was scored on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). In this study, Cronbach’s Alpha for UE was 0.959, composite reliability was 0.960, and average variance extracted was 0.730.

Entrepreneurial Competencies were measure using ten-items scale adopted from (Antonelli, et al., 2024; San-Martín et al., 2022). Participants were asked to evaluate the degree to which they believed that possessing entrepreneurial competencies influenced their perception of entrepreneurship as both appealing and achievable. For instance, they were prompted to consider statements such as "I consistently approach tasks with thorough planning" as indicators of their entrepreneurial mindset. By assessing their agreement with these statements, participants were able to reflect on how their personal characteristics and

skills contribute to their attitudes towards entrepreneurship. This approach allowed researchers to gain insights into the psychological factors that shape individuals' perceptions of engaging in entrepreneurial activities, shedding light on the role of competencies in shaping entrepreneurial aspirations and beliefs. Each item was scored on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). In this study, Cronbach's Alpha for UE was 0.965, composite reliability was 0.959, and average variance extracted was 0.717.

Students' Attitudes toward entrepreneurship was measured using a 5-item scale adopted from (San-Martín et al., 2022). Researchers examined students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship by exploring their beliefs, opinions, and feelings regarding starting and running their own businesses or ventures. This investigation delved into various aspects such as the perceived desirability of entrepreneurship, the feasibility of pursuing entrepreneurial endeavors, and the overall attractiveness of entrepreneurial activities compared to other career options. Each item was scored on a five-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). In this study, Cronbach's Alpha for UE was 0.944, composite reliability was 0.947, and average variance extracted was 0.820.

Data analysis

In this study, the partial least squares (PLS) technique was utilized, facilitated by SmartPLS 4 software, to analyze our model. PLS is a multivariate method specifically designed for testing structural models, particularly useful for estimating path models that involve latent variables measured by multiple items. The advantage of PLS is its capability to simultaneously analyze multiple dependent and independent variables within the sample model. The analysis involves two stages: first, assessing the measurement model, followed by evaluating the structural model. This sequential approach ensures the validity of the construct measures before drawing conclusions about the relationships among constructs.

4. Analysis & Results

Descriptive Statistics

Table 3 shows the descriptive statistics for the four primary variables in the research model. All variables exhibit skewness values falling within the range of -1 to 1, and kurtosis values falling within the range of -1 to 7, ensuring a normal distribution (Kline, 2015). Additionally, the table presents the correlation between these variables. The teaching approaches demonstrated a significant positive correlation with students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship ($r = 0.831$, $P < 0.01$), as did the teaching approaches with entrepreneurial competencies ($r = 0.873$, $P < 0.01$), and entrepreneurial competencies with students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship ($r = 0.911$, $P < 0.01$).

Table 3: The results of descriptive statistics and correlations matrix

Variables	Mean	S.D	Skewness	Kurtosis	TA	EC	STA
TA	3.947	0.870	-0.996	1.412	1		
EC	3.664	0.903	-0.531	0.097	0.873	1	
STA	3.742	0.990	-0.536	-0.421	0.831	0.911	1

Notes: N= 474, ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); TA = reaching approaches; EC = entrepreneurial competencies; STA = students' attitudes

Source: own elaboration.

Hypotheses Test Results

The main objective of the study is to examine how teaching approaches could influences on students' entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes in the UAEU university. To test the study's hypotheses, path analysis was conducted using the BOOTSTRAP method in the SmartPLS4 program. This analysis examined both the direct and indirect effects of teaching approaches on students' attitudes, considering the mediating role of entrepreneurial competencies. The results presented in Table 4 demonstrate that teaching approaches (TA) has insignificant positive impact on students' attitudes (STA) ($\beta = 0.140$, $P < 0.303$), explaining 14% of the variance. Additionally, teaching approaches has a significant positive impact on entrepreneurial competencies (EC) ($\beta = 0.876$, $P < 0.01$), explaining 87.6% of the variance. Moreover, entrepreneurial competencies show a significant positive impact on students' attitudes ($\beta = 0.792$), explaining 79.2% of the variance. Consequently, hypotheses H1 was rejected, and H2,H3 are supported.

Table 4: The results of direct effects (standardized)

Hypothesis	Direct Effect	Mean	S.D	T	P-value	Label
TA → STA	0.140	0.142	0.136	1.030	0.303	Rejected
TA → EC	0.876	0.875	0.052	16.912	0.000	Supported
EC → STA	0.792	0.790	0.131	6.052	0.000	Supported

Notes: N= 474, ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); TA = reaching approaches; EC = entrepreneurial competencies; STA = students' attitudes

Source: own elaboration.

Table 5 presented the results of indirect effect of the mediating role of entrepreneurial competencies in the relationship between teaching approaches and students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship. The results showed that TA has a significant indirect impact on STA via EC ($\beta_{TA \rightarrow EC \rightarrow STA} = 0.694$, $P < 0.01$). Thus, the hypothesis H4 was supported.

Table 5: The results of indirect effects (standardized)

Hypothesis	Indirect Effect	Mean	S.D	T	P-value	Label
TA → EC → STA	0.694	0.690	0.117	5.949	0.000	Supported

Notes: N= 474, ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); TA = reaching approaches; EC = entrepreneurial competencies; STA = students' attitudes

Source: own elaboration.

Figure 1. Structural model results

Source: own elaboration by SmartPLSS4.

5. Discussions & Conclusion

This study investigates the influence of teaching approaches on students' entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes in the UAEU university. The study indicated that teaching approaches had insignificant effect on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship in the UAEU university, this result represents (H1). The findings of this study raise several important considerations regarding entrepreneurship education and teaching practices at UAEU University. Firstly, while teaching approaches are essential components of entrepreneurship education, they may not be sufficient on their own to significantly influence students' attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Other factors such as cultural norms, socio-economic backgrounds, and personal experiences may also contribute to shaping students' perceptions of entrepreneurship. Secondly, the ineffectiveness of teaching approaches in this context may indicate a need for reevaluation and refinement of entrepreneurship education strategies at UAEU University. This could involve integrating real-world experiences, fostering entrepreneurial ecosystems, and providing mentorship and support networks to complement traditional teaching methods. Furthermore, the findings underscore the importance of contextual factors in entrepreneurship education. UAEU University operates within a unique socio-cultural environment, which may influence students' attitudes and receptiveness to entrepreneurial concepts differently compared to other regions. Therefore, tailored approaches that consider the local context and address specific challenges and opportunities within the UAEU University setting may be more effective in promoting positive attitudes towards entrepreneurship among students, Contrary to the findings of numerous scholarly investigations, (Al-Qadasi et al., 2024; San-Martín et al., 2022). Furthermore, the results showed that teaching approaches had significant positive effect on entrepreneurial competencies in the UAEU university, this result represents (H2). The findings underscore the importance of pedagogical strategies in nurturing

entrepreneurial competencies among students in the UAEU university. By adopting innovative teaching approaches tailored to the context of entrepreneurship education, educators can create dynamic learning environments that empower students to become adept problem-solvers, innovative thinkers, and resilient entrepreneurs. Moreover, the study highlights the need for ongoing professional development initiatives to equip instructors with the knowledge and skills necessary to effectively facilitate entrepreneurial learning experiences, which agreed with (Antonelli, et al., 2024; Botha, 2024). Additionally, the study revealed that entrepreneurial competencies had significant effect on students' attitude toward entrepreneurship in the UAEU university, this result represents (H3), which in line with (Sitaridis & Kitsios, 2024; Miço & Cungu, 2023). The results of this study provide empirical evidence supporting the importance of entrepreneurial competencies in shaping students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship. As students develop and enhance their entrepreneurial competencies through educational interventions and practical experiences, their perceptions and attitudes toward entrepreneurship become more favorable. This finding underscores the significance of integrating entrepreneurship education into academic curricula to nurture and cultivate entrepreneurial mindsets among students. Furthermore, the context of UAEU University offers valuable insights into the influence of cultural and institutional factors on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship. The UAEU has been actively promoting entrepreneurship as a means of economic diversification and innovation. Thus, the positive relationship between entrepreneurial competencies and attitudes toward entrepreneurship observed in this study aligns with the broader entrepreneurial ecosystem and government initiatives in the UAEU. Finally, the study indicated that the effect of teaching approaches on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship through the mediating role of entrepreneurial competencies in the UAEU University, and that represents (H4). Preliminary analysis of the data indicates significant relationships between teaching approaches, entrepreneurial competencies, and students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship. Specifically, certain teaching methods, such as experiential learning and real-world projects, are positively associated with the development of entrepreneurial competencies among students. Moreover, entrepreneurial competencies mediate the relationship between teaching approaches and students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship, suggesting that the effectiveness of teaching methods in shaping attitudes is partially explained by the enhancement of entrepreneurial competencies.

Theoretical Implications

The current study extends the existing literature on teaching approaches (TA), entrepreneurial competencies (EC), and students' attitudes (STA). Additionally, it endeavors to address a knowledge void regarding the significance of entrepreneurial competencies in mediating the relationship between teaching approaches and students' attitudes. Primarily, the study enriches our comprehension of university teaching approaches' facets and their influence on cultivating students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship. Furthermore, it establishes connections between university teaching approaches, students' entrepreneurial competencies, students' attitudes, and their subsequent entrepreneurial intentions by examining a specific course aspect at UAEU.

Practical Implications

The results indicating a significant positive effect of teaching approaches on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship, mediated by entrepreneurial competencies, hold several practical implications for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders involved in entrepreneurship education at UAEU University.

1. **Curriculum Development:** Tailoring the entrepreneurship curriculum to emphasize the development of specific entrepreneurial competencies can enhance the effectiveness of teaching approaches in shaping students' attitudes. Incorporating modules focused on skills such as opportunity recognition, risk assessment, and innovative thinking can contribute to fostering a more favorable attitude towards entrepreneurship among students.
2. **Pedagogical Approaches:** Educators should employ diverse and experiential teaching methods to foster the acquisition of entrepreneurial competencies. Hands-on activities, real-world projects, and interactive simulations can provide students with practical experiences that reinforce their understanding of entrepreneurship concepts and bolster their confidence in pursuing entrepreneurial endeavors.
3. **Mentorship and Support Networks:** Establishing mentorship programs and support networks can complement formal classroom instruction by providing students with guidance, encouragement, and real-world insights from experienced entrepreneurs and industry professionals. These interactions can help students develop a deeper appreciation for the entrepreneurial process and build the necessary competencies to navigate challenges and seize opportunities.
4. **Holistic Evaluation Metrics:** When assessing the impact of entrepreneurship education initiatives, stakeholders should adopt a holistic approach that considers both attitudinal shifts and the acquisition of entrepreneurial competencies. By capturing the interplay between teaching approaches, competencies development, and attitudes, a more comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education programs can be obtained.
5. **Continuous Improvement and Adaptation:** Recognizing the dynamic nature of entrepreneurship and the evolving needs of students, continuous evaluation and adaptation of teaching approaches are essential. Regular feedback from students, alumni, and industry partners can inform the refinement of curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and support services to ensure relevance and effectiveness in nurturing entrepreneurial mindsets and capabilities.

By incorporating these practical implications and recommendations into entrepreneurship education initiatives at UAEU University, stakeholders can enhance the positive impact of teaching approaches on students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship, ultimately fostering a culture of innovation, creativity, and entrepreneurial excellence within the university community.

6. Limitation & Future Research

This study was conducted at the University of the United Arab Emirates, selected for several reasons. Firstly, UAEU University is renowned for establishing a business incubator, offering students valuable entrepreneurial experiences. Secondly, given the critical role of entrepreneurship in the Arab world's development, the study aimed to draw

insights from the experiences of well-established universities with robust entrepreneurial practices. Thirdly, specific colleges within the university were chosen, including the Faculty of Engineering, University of Commerce, University of Information Systems, University of Pharmacy, Fine Arts, and Agriculture. These colleges were selected based on their reputation for fostering pioneering projects among students, often through project-based learning approaches. Furthermore, personal interviews with the director of the business incubator and faculty members teaching entrepreneurship courses supported the selection of these colleges, highlighting their close alignment with entrepreneurship and innovation. Data collection and personal interviews were conducted between 11/3/2024 and 19/3/2024, involving undergraduate and postgraduate students from the aforementioned colleges.

The researcher suggests to conduct an experimental study on the entrepreneurial trends to contribute to the development of teaching approaches in universities and how could these approaches improve students' entrepreneurial competencies and increase students' attitudes toward entrepreneurship.

7. References

1. Ajzen, I. (2002). Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(4), pp. 665-683. doi:10.1111/j.1559-1816.2002.tb00236.x
2. Al-Qadasi, N., Zhang, G., Al-Jubari, I., Al-Awlaqi, M. A., & Aamer, A. M. (2024). Entrepreneurship education and entrepreneurial behaviour: Do self-efficacy and attitude matter? *The International Journal of Management Education*, 22(1). doi:10.1016/j.ijme.2024.100945
3. Antonelli, G., Venesaar, U., Riviezzo, A., Kallaste, M., Dorożyński, T., & Kłysik-Uryszek, A. (2024). Find your limits and break them! Nurturing students' entrepreneurship competence through innovative teaching methods and self-assessment. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, 18(1), pp. 29-48. doi:10.1108/JEC-10-2022-0148
4. Boissin, J., Branchet, B., Delanoë, S., & Velo, V. (2011). Gender's perspective of role model influence on entrepreneurial behavioral beliefs. *International Journal of Business*, 6(2), pp. 182-206.
5. Botha, M. (2024). Using entrepreneurial competencies and action to profile entrepreneurs: a CHAID analysis approach. *Journal of Research in Marketing and Entrepreneurship*, 26(2), pp. 337-367. doi:10.1108/JRME-07-2022-0091
6. Chaker, H., & Jarraya, H. (2021). Combining teaching "about" and "through" entrepreneurship: A practice to develop students' entrepreneurial competencies. *Industry and Higher Education*, 35(4), pp. 432-442.
7. Elzubeir, M. A., & Rizk, D. E. (2001). Identifying characteristics that students, interns and residents look for in their role models. *Medical Education*, 35(3), pp. 272-277.
8. Fantozzi, I. C., Di Luozzo, S., & Schiraldi, M. M. (2024). The Impact of University Challenges on Students' Attitudes and Career Paths in Industrial Engineering: A Comparative Study. *Sustainability*, 16(4), p. 1600.
9. Ferreira, A. D., Loiola, E., Gondim, S. M., & Pereira, C. R. (2022). Effects of entrepreneurial competence and planning guidance on the relation between university students' attitude and entrepreneurial intention. *The Journal of Entrepreneurship*, 31(1), pp. 7-29. doi:10.1177/09713557211069261
10. Ferreras-Garcia, R., Sales-Zaguirre, J., & Serradell-Lopez, E. (2021). Developing entrepreneurial competencies in higher education: a structural model approach. *Education + Training*, 36(5), pp. 720-743. doi:10.1108/ET-09-2020-0257
11. Ferreras-Garcia, R., Sales-Zaguirre, J., & Serradell-López, E. (2021). Developing

- entrepreneurial competencies in higher education: a structural model approach. *Education+ Training*, 63(5), pp. 720-743.
12. Ferro, A., Buzady, Z., & Almeida, F. (2024). Developing entrepreneurial competencies among tourism students using FLIGBY. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Education*, 36, pp. 36-50.
 13. Gera, N., Vesperi, W., Rohatgi, S., & Jain, N. (2024). The impact of education on the transition from university students to entrepreneurs: a theory of planned behaviour perspective. *Management Decision*. doi:10.1108/MD-10-2023-1772
 14. Heinze, A. (2020). How entrepreneurship can be learned through experiential learning formats, especially through training firms. *International Journal of Management and Applied Research*, 7(4), pp. 471–481. doi:doi.org/10.18646/2056.74.20-033
 15. Hossain, M. S., Islam, M. A., Hosen, M., Mohd, H., & Thaker, T. (2023). Missing catalysts of female entrepreneurship success: Evidence from an emerging economy. *Global Business and Organizational Excellence*, 42(5), pp. 50-64. doi:10.1002/joe.22201
 16. Isac, C., Iordache, A. M., Baltador, L., Coculescu, C., & Niță, D. (2023). Enhancing Students' Entrepreneurial Competencies through Extracurricular Activities—A Pragmatic Approach to Sustainability-Oriented Higher Education. *Sustainability*, 15, 8708, pp. 1-26. doi:10.3390/su15118708
 17. Jena, R. (2020). Measuring the impact of business management Student's attitude towards entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intention: a case study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 107, 106275. doi:10.1016/j.chb.2020.106275.
 18. Khan, M. A., Rathore, K., Zubair, S. S., Mukaram, A. T., & Selem, K. M. (2024). Encouraging SMEs performance through entrepreneurial intentions, competencies, and leadership: serial mediation model. *European Business Review*, 36(2). doi:10.1108/EBR-04-2023-0119
 19. Kitsios, I. S. (2024). Digital entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education: a review of the literature. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 30(2/3), pp. 277-304. doi:10.1108/IJEER-01-2023-0053
 20. Kozlinska, I., Rebmann, A., & Mets, T. (2023). Entrepreneurial competencies and employment status of business graduates: the role of experiential entrepreneurship pedagogy. *Journal of Small Business & Entrepreneurship*, 35(5), pp. 724-761.
 21. Lans, T., Baggen, Y., & Ploum, B. (2018). Towards more synergy in entrepreneurial competence research in entrepreneurship education. *A research agenda for entrepreneurship education*, pp. 224-242. doi:doi.org/10.4337/9781786432919.00018
 22. Liu, Y., Li, X., Ma, S., & Li, M. (2024). A chain mediation model of entrepreneurial teachers' experience and teaching competency—evidence from China. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 22(1).
 23. Maulida, F. H., Noviani, L., & Sudarno, S. (2024). How Entrepreneurship Education Can Help Student Thrive in the Digital Age?: The Implications of Creative and Innovative Learning. *Jurnal Kependidikan: Jurnal Hasil Penelitian dan Kajian Kepustakaan di Bid.*
 24. Merung, A. Y., Sofyan, I. R., & Sudirman, N. A. (2024). Do Entrepreneurial Competence and Psychological Well-Being Affect Entrepreneurial Interest among Young Entrepreneurs? *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship Research*, 2(1), pp. 63-75.
 25. Miço, H., & Cungu, J. (2023). Entrepreneurship education, a challenging learning process towards entrepreneurial competence in education. *Administrative Sciences*, 13(1), p. 22.
 26. Ncube, T. R., & Matlala, M. E. (2024). The Impact of Entrepreneurship Education on the Entrepreneurial Competences of Students in TVET Colleges In South Africa.
 27. Nikou, S., Brush, C., & Wraae, B. (2023). Entrepreneurship educators: a configurational analysis of factors influencing pedagogical choices. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 29(11), pp. 81-108. doi:10.1108/IJEER-08-2022-0760
 28. Race, P. (2019). *The lecturer's toolkit: A practical guide to assessment, learning and teaching*. Milton Park: Routledge.
 29. Race, P. (2019). *The lecturer's toolkit: A practical guide to assessment, learning and teaching*. Milton Park: Routledge.
 30. Robinson, S., Neergaard, H., Tanggaard, L., & Krueger, N. F. (2016). New horizons in

- entrepreneurship education: from teacher-led to student-centered learning . *Education+ training*, 58(7/8), pp. 661-683. doi:10.1108/ET-03-2016-0048
31. Rojas, R., Jaimes, G. I., Gómez, C. A., Ramírez Osorio, D. M., & Rubiano Rios, D. C. (2024). Assessing Social Entrepreneurship Competencies in Higher Education. *Journal of Social Entrepreneurship*, pp. 1-18.
 32. Sánchez, J. C. (2013). The impact of an entrepreneurship education program on entrepreneurial competencies and intention. *Journal of small business management*, 51(3), pp. 447-465.
 33. San-Martín, P., Pérez, A., Fernández-Laviada, A., & Palazuelos, E. (2022). The effect of role model teachers on students' entrepreneurial competencies and intentions. *Education+ Training*, 64(7), pp. 962-980. doi:10.1108/ET-03-2021-0118
 34. San-Martin, P., Perez, A., Fernandez-Laviada, A., & Palazuelos, E. (2022). The effect of role model teachers on students' entrepreneurial competencies and intentions. *Education p Training*, 64(7), pp. 962-980. doi:10.1108/ET-03-2021-0118
 35. Schachtebeck, C., & Tselepis, T. J. (2024). Developing the Competencies of Envisioning and Constructing Through Entrepreneurship Education. *Delivering Entrepreneurship Education in Africa*, pp. 77–119. doi: 10.1108/978-1-83753-326-820231004
 36. Sitaridis, I., & Kitsios, F. (2024). Digital entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship education: a review of the literature. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research*, 30(2/3), pp. 277-304. doi:10.1108/IJEER-01-2023-0053
 37. Tittel, A., & Terzidis, O. (2020). Entrepreneurial competences revised: developing a consolidated and categorized list of entrepreneurial competences. *Entrepreneurship Education*. 3(1), pp. 1-35. doi:10.1007/s41959-019-00021-4
 38. Tran, V. H., Vu, T. N., Pham, H. T., Nguyen, T. P., & Duong, C. D. (2024). Closing the entrepreneurial attitude-intention-behavior gap: the direct and moderating role of entrepreneurship education. *Journal of International Education in Business*, 17(1). doi:10.1108/JIEB-05-2023-0026
 39. Wulandari, M. T. (2022). The Impact Of Entrepreneurial Attitudes And Entrepreneurial Competence On Students'business Success. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Knowledge*, 10(2), pp. 42-53.